

and the latter, 273. At 35 days after transplanting the roots of treated seedlings had 4.7 nematodes/g root; the

roots in the check plots had 10.2 nematodes/g root. At harvest the former had 3 nematodes/plant and the

latter, 29/plant. Plots with the treated seedlings yielded 85% more than the check plots (1.5 kg vs 0.81 kg/plot). ■

Further studies on the potential of weeds to spread tungro in West Bengal, India

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In a previous study on the potential of weeds to spread rice tungro in West Bengal, no virus occurred naturally on the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field. But *Echinochloa colona* and *Paspalum notatum* inoculated with the virus kept it for 3 months. In

a further study of weeds' potential for spreading rice tungro virus, weeds were collected from different locations early in different crop seasons.

The following weeds were collected in April 1978 and in June 1978: *Echinochloa colona*, *Paspalum notatum*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eleusine indica*, *Cyperus iria*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Setaria glauca*, *Sporobolus diander*, *Cyperus esculentus*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Dicanthium annulatum*, *Brachiaria ramosa*, and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. Only *L. hexandra* was not obtained in June but another species,

Digitaria sanguinalis, was available. In November 1978 only nine weeds (*E. colona*, *C. dactylon*, *P. notatum*, *S. diander*, *C. esculentus*, *D. annulatum*, *I. cylindrica*, *B. Ramosa*, and *Cyperus rotundus*) were collected. None showed any virus except a few collections of *E. colona* from the endemic fields of Malda.

The weeds were then inoculated with the tungro virus and their retention of the virus was indexed on TN1 seedlings (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from weeds collected 2 to 5 months after inoculation, Kalyani, West Bengal, India, 1978.

Weed	Transmission (%)											
	April				June				November			
	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo	2 mo	3 mo	4 mo	5 mo
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	15	10	5	X	20	10	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	X	X	X	X	25	15	10	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X	X	20	10	X	X
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	X	X	X	X	20	10	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Paspalum notatum</i>	X	X	X	X	30	20	10	X	10	X	X	X
<i>Setaria glauca</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Sporobolus diander</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Dicanthium annulatum</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i>	X	X	X	X	10	X	X	X	X	X	Y	X
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

1979 setback for ufra

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Ufra disease, caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (Filipjev) is serious in deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. It was particularly severe around the village of Kashimpur in Comilla district, almost at the northern limit of its distribution in southeastern

Bangladesh, according to disease surveys in November 1977 and 1978. In 1979, the disease disappeared from the area; no plants with symptoms were found during September. The average number of nematodes per stem in 6 fields about

80 m apart along a linear transect at Kashimpur was estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4[3] June 1979:10) at about the end of September (i.e. just before panicle initiation) in 1979 and in 1979 (see

Average number of nematodes per stem in 6 deepwater rice fields along a transect at Kashimpur, Bangladesh, 1978 and 1979.

Date	Sample size (stems/field)	Nematodes (av no./stem)						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2 Oct 1978	15	— ^a	1421 ^b	9	49	786 ^{bc}	250	989 ^b
24 Sep 1979	50	4	— ^a	1	1	6	1	1

^aNo deepwater rice. ^bIncludes stems containing more than 3,000 nematodes. ^cThis crop was a total loss because of ufra in 1978.